

Original Article

The clinical utility of urinary N-acetyl-β-D-glucosaminidase[NAG] creatinine ratio in the assessment of diabetic nephropathy in a tertiary hospital in Eastern Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Tubular injury, as shown by the detection of tubular damage markers in the urine, is a critical component of the early course of Diabetic Nephropathy (DN). Urinary excretion of tubular markers such as urinary N-acetyl-β-D-glucosaminidase (NAG) may be useful in assessing an initial malfunction or damage of the renal tubules in the early stage of DN. This study was to assess the clinical usefulness of NAG/creatinine ratio in evaluating kidney dysfunction in type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM) patients. This was a cross-sectional analytical study of 283 type 2 DM patients at the Federal Medical Centre (FMC), Owerri, Nigeria. Ethical approval was obtained from the Research and Ethics Committee of FMC, Owerri. Data obtained was analyzed using IBM-SPSS version 21.0. A p-value of <0.05 was considered significant for all statistical comparisons. The mean age of patients studied was 56±13.41 years. Of the patients studied, 87 patients were normoalbuminuric while 196 had microalbuminuria. The mean NAG/creatinine ratio for normoalbuminuric diabetics was significantly lower (p<0.001) than values obtained in patients with microalbuminuria. In addition, 28.7% and 57.7% of normoalbuminuric and microalbuminuric diabetics respectively had elevated urinary NAG/creatinine ratio. Higher Urinary NAG excretion in microalbuminuric diabetics represents an early marker of incipient diabetic nephropathy buttressing that early NAG excretion at elevated levels is a significant marker of susceptibility to DN and its assessment may help identify diabetics with predisposition to DN.

Keywords: Diabetes Mellitus, Diabetic Nephropathy, N-acetyl-β-D-glucosaminidase, Urinary biomarker.

INTRODUCTION

The number of people with diabetes has risen from 108 million in 1980 to 422 million in 2014.⁽¹⁾ The global prevalence of diabetes among adults over 18 years of age has risen from 4.7% in 1980 to 8.5% in 2014.¹ Diabetes prevalence has been rising more rapidly in middle- and low-income countries.¹

Diabetic nephropathy is a clinical syndrome characterized by the following: persistent

albuminuria (>300mg/dl or >200μg/min) that is confirmed on at least 2 occasions 3-6 months apart; progressive decline in the glomerular filtration rate (GFR) and elevated arterial blood pressure.² Diabetic nephropathy (DN) is a dreaded complication of diabetes mellitus as it results in significant morbidity / mortality and is encountered in approximately 20 - 40% of type 1 and <20% of type 2 diabetic patients.²

This major life-threatening complication develops in approximately 20 - 40% of type 1 and less than

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20% of type 2 diabetic patients.³ Currently, in most of the developed countries diabetes is the leading cause of chronic kidney disease, and is known to account for about 45% of kidney failure worldwide.⁴ For example in the United States of America, it accounts for an estimated 28,000 new cases of End Stage Renal Disease (ESRD) per year.⁵ A recent study also suggests that DN may be assuming an increasing role as a cause of Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) in Africa.⁶ In Nigeria due to the increasing prevalence of diabetes mellitus there is a concomitant increase in the incidence of diabetic nephropathy.⁷

In the absence of specific interventions, about 80% of patients with type-I diabetes with sustained microalbuminuria progress to the stage of overt nephropathy or clinical microalbuminuria (defined as urinary albumin excretion rate [AER] >300 mg/24 hours, >200 mg/min in a timed collection, or >300 µg/mg creatinine in a spot urine) over a period of 10 to 15 years.⁸⁻¹⁰ However, in patients who develop microalbuminuria late in the course of the disease (after more than 15 to 29 years), the risk of developing overt renal disease is only about 1% per year. ESRD develops in 50% of type-I diabetes patients with overt nephropathy within 10 years and in more than 75% by 20 years in the absence of treatment.⁸ A greater proportion of patients with type-2 diabetes compared with type-I diabetes have microalbuminuria and overt nephropathy at or shortly after diagnosis of diabetes.⁹ This is because the disease may have been present for several years before the diagnosis is made.¹⁰

Recently, changes in the renal tubules, which is termed diabetic tubulopathy, are increasingly implicated in the development of progressive diabetic kidney disease.^{11,12} Interestingly, some of these tubular damage markers already are elevated in normoalbuminuric diabetic patients with normal estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR).¹³ Tubular injury, as shown by the detection of tubular damage markers in the urine, is a critical component of the early course of DN and has been suggested to contribute in a primary way, rather than a secondary manner, to the development of early DN.^{14,15} Urinary excretion of these tubular markers would be useful in assessing an initial malfunction or damage of the

renal tubules in the early stage of DN.

Several tubular damage markers, discovered recently have clinical implications as markers for the development and progression of DN.^{16,17} They include urinary neutrophil gelatinase associated lipocalin [NGAL],^{13,18} kidney injury molecule-1 [KIM-1],¹⁹ liver-type fatty acid binding protein [L-FABP],²⁰ N-acetyl-beta-D-glucosaminidase [NAG],²¹ beta(β) 2-microglobulin [B2-M]²² and retinol binding protein [RBP].²³

A significant number of urinary markers suggesting renal tubular injury have been discovered with significant sensitivity and specificity. The urinary N-acetyl-β-D glucosaminidase (NAG) is one of the urinary markers of tubular injury that can be used to detect early nephropathy clinically.²⁴ N-acetyl-β-D-glucosaminidase, is a high-molecular-weight (14-16KDa) lysosomal enzyme which occur in high concentrations in lysosomes of renal proximal tubule²⁵ that cannot pass into the ultra-filtrate because of its size. The urinary excretion of enzymes, in particular N-acetyl-β-D-glucosaminidase (NAG), is considered a relatively simple, cheap, fast and non-invasive method in the detection and follow-up of renal tubular function. Before the onset of gross structural changes in the renal tubules, lysosomal enzymes like NAG have been found to markedly increase in urine.²⁶ Therefore, the determination of urinary NAG provides a very sensitive and reliable indicator of renal damage, such as injury or dysfunction due to diabetes mellitus.²⁷

Urinary NAG activity is an extremely sensitive index of renal parenchymal insult²⁸ and it is therefore a reliable test to use in monitoring the progression of kidney diseases.²⁹ Urine NAG activity is widely used to evaluate tubular renal function³⁰ and thus it is a measure of altered function in the renal tubules and not simply an indicator of damage.³¹ Patients with normal and abnormal renal function can be differentiated by analysis of NAG activity in untimed specimens of urine. Certain characteristics of NAG that have made it a good marker for assessing tubular dysfunction include- little diurnal fluctuation in the rate of NAG excretion,²⁹ variations in urine flow can reliably be compensated by relating

urine NAG activity to urine creatinine concentration,³² NAG activity is not increased by bacterial colonization of urine, urinary NAG activity is usually normal in subjects with postural proteinuria, and also urine specimens can be stored for several days at 4-6°C and, for months at -20 °C without change in NAG activity.³³⁻³⁵

Urinary activities of NAG are elevated in patients with diabetes when compared with non-diabetic control subjects and showed a significant positive correlation with serum cystatin C, serum creatinine, urinary albumin excretion (UAE), and urinary albumin creatinine ratio (UACR) and an inverse correlation with measured and estimated creatinine clearance (CrCl) in all patients, indicating the possible clinical application of urinary NAG as a complementary marker for early detection of DN.³⁵ It also correlates positively with disease duration and poor glycemic control (HbA1c).³⁵⁻³⁷

Thus, detection of tubular damage in diabetics can be used to detect early DN and aid in institution of strategies to prevent or slow down development of overt DN and development of ESRD. This concept formed the need for this study in a resource poor economy like ours where management of ESRD is capital intensive and unaffordable by majority of Nigerians.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This was a cross-sectional analytical study conducted at Federal Medical Centre, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria. Two hundred and eighty three consenting type II diabetes mellitus patients diagnosed according to the World Health Organization criteria, 2006,³⁸ who met the inclusion criteria were recruited for the study. Diabetic patients with sickle cell disease, history or renal ultrasound features suggestive of urinary tract structural abnormalities, history suggestive of urinary tract infection in the one month preceding the date of study, haematuria, history of aminoglycoside use or other drugs predisposing to proteinuria in the two weeks preceding the day of interview, history of angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitor (ACEI) or angiotensin receptor blocker (ARB) use in the preceding two weeks, evidence of elevated serum

creatinine or features of uraemia or chronic kidney disease or a history of fever were excluded from the study.

Ethical approval was obtained from the Research and Ethics Committee of the Federal Medical Centre, Owerri, Imo State. Data obtained was analyzed using IBM-SPSS version 21.0. A p-value of < 0.05 was considered significant for all statistical comparisons.

RESULTS

The mean age of diabetic patients was 56±13.41 years. There was a total of 162 (57.2%) female and 121 (42.8%) male diabetic patients with a male to female ratio of 1.3:1. Most of the diabetic patients, 166 (58.6%) were found to be in the age class of 41-60 years. The majority; 257 (90.8%) of the diabetic patients were married with about 51.9% (n=147) having attained tertiary form of education.

Most of the diabetic patients, 183 (64.7%) have had diabetes for less than five years, while 63 (22.3%) and 37 (13.1%) had diabetes for six to ten years and >10 years respectively. The mean duration of the diabetes was 7.84 (±5.42) years. Over half (n=166) of diabetics (58.7%) had a positive family history of diabetes with 28.6% (n=81) having a positive family history of hypertension while 12 (4.2%) patients had a family history of kidney disease.

The mean packed cell volume was 33.13 ± 3.22% with 9.2% (n=26) of diabetics having anaemia. Furthermore, the diabetic population had a mean serum creatinine value of 85.96±46.71 μmol/l with elevated levels observed in 6.4% (n=18) of diabetics. Also, the mean estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) was 119.22 ± 55.74 ml/min/1.73m² with 32.5% (n=92) of the diabetics having a reduced eGFR. [Table 1]

The mean fasting blood glucose in the diabetic population was 177.21±76.52 mg/dl. Two hundred and thirty (81.3%) diabetics had an elevated fasting blood glucose (FBG) level, while 53 of them (18.7%) had normal values. Also, 234 (82.7%) of the diabetic patients at presentation had elevated glycosylated haemoglobin HbA1c levels, with the mean HbA1c being 8.59±6.48%. [Table 1]

The mean urinary NAG values estimated for the diabetic group (283) was 8.67 ± 2.67 units with the mean in males being 9.12 ± 3.02 units and 8.24 ± 2.33 units in females. While the mean NAG/Cr estimate was 7.12 ± 5.11 U/g.

In this study, 87(30.7%) of diabetics were normoalbuminuric, while 196(69.3%) were microalbuminuric. [Figure 1] Normoalbuminuric diabetics had a mean (SD) NAG/creatinine ratio of 5.78 ± 2.97 U/g while Microalbuminuric diabetics had a mean (SD) NAG/creatinine ratio of 7.12 ± 5.11 U/g. This difference was statistically significant with ($p < 0.001$)

A regression analysis was used to determine a cut-off value for elevated urinary NAG/creatinine ratio was set at >7.62 U/g. Using this criterion, Twenty seven (28.7%) of normoalbuminuric diabetic patients had elevated urinary NAG/creatinine ratio which was significantly lower than 113 (57.7%) microalbuminuric diabetics who had elevated urinary NAG/creatinine ratio [$\chi^2 = 17.08$; $p < 0.001$; OR(CI) = 0.33 (0.19 – 0.58)]. [Figure 1]

In addition, Pearson's correlation between clinical/biochemical parameters and urinary NAG/Creatinine ratio showed a significant negative correlation between serum creatinine ($p = 0.006$), estimated glomerular filtration rate ($p = 0.022$) and urinary NAG/Creatinine ratio values. [Table 2]

Table 1: Clinical and biochemical profile of patients

Clinical Parameters	Mean \pm SD	Percentage of Population with abnormal findings
Packed Cell Volume (%)	33.13 \pm 3.22	Reduced in 9.2% (n = 26)
Serum Creatinine ($\mu\text{mol/l}$)	85.96 \pm 46.71	Elevated in 6.4% (n = 18)
Serum Urea (mmol/l)	11.76 \pm 6.91	Reduced in 3.2% (n = 9)
eGFR (ml/min/1.73m ²)	119.22 \pm 55.74	Reduced in 32.5% (n = 92)
FBS (mg/dl)	177.21 \pm 76.52	Elevated in 81.3% (n = 230)
HbA1c (%)	8.59 \pm 6.48	Elevated in 82.7% (n = 234)

** percentages calculated using total number of diabetics [N= 283]
Figure 1: Prevalence of microalbuminuria and Elevated urinary NAG/creatinine ratio

Table 2: The relationship between selected parameters and urinary NAG/creatinine ratio

	Urinary NAG/creatinine ratio	
	r	P
Age (Years)	0.111	0.06
BMI (Kg/m ²)	0.014	0.82
SBP (mmHg)	0.034	0.56
DBP (mmHg)	0.016	0.79
WHR	-0.102	0.08
FBG (mg/dl)	-0.038	0.53
HbA1c (%)	-0.065	0.28
ACR (mg/g)	0.088	0.14
Serum creatinine (μmol)	0.163	0.006*
eGFR (ml/min/1.73m ²)	-0.216	0.022*

BMI-body mass index; SBP- systolic blood pressure; DBP- diastolic blood pressure;
WHR-waist hip ratio; FBG-fasting blood glucose; HbA1c-glycated haemoglobin;
ACR-albumin creatinine ratio; eGFR-estimated glomerular filtration rate *significant at $p < 0.05$

DISCUSSION

The sex ratio of participants was 1.3:1 with a female preponderance probably because females tend to have a better health seeking behavior compared to males. The mean age of the diabetic population was 56 ± 13.41 years similar to the study conducted by Ekrikpo et al.²⁴

The prevalence of family history of diabetes and that of renal disease as seen in the patients' studied, is in keeping with a strong family history being an important risk factor for disease manifestation as earlier reported among diabetics of Afro-American origin as well as Caucasians.³⁹

Urinary NAG is a hydrolytic lysosomal enzyme found predominantly in proximal tubule. It has been demonstrated as a marker of renal tubular impairment in various conditions involved with renal injury or dysfunction.²⁷ Urinary activities of NAG are elevated in patients with diabetes as seen in this study where it also showed an inverse significant correlation with serum creatinine and eGFR, indicating the possible clinical application of urinary NAG as a complementary marker for early detection of tubular involvement as seen in diabetic nephropathy.⁴⁰

Existing literature has shown that elevated NAG and NAG/creatinine levels suggest the role of tubular dysfunction commonly seen in diabetics with

nephropathy, and is thus a reliable test in monitoring the progression of kidney diseases.²⁹ In addition, previous studies have also shown that Urine NAG activity, can be used to evaluate tubular renal function³⁰ and thus it is a measure of altered function in the renal tubules and not simply an indicator of damage.³¹

Urinary NAG excretion has been found in both groups of diabetic patients although found to be significantly higher in microalbuminuric than normoalbuminuric patients. Notably, it has been suggested that urinary NAG excretion is higher in diabetic patients than normal populations, even before they develop microalbuminuria.^{37,41} It's presence even in patients with normoalbuminuria is important as it indicates the importance of NAG in detecting renal tubule cell damage, especially at the early stage before the appearance of microalbuminuria.⁴² Urinary NAG activities tend to be present in diabetic patients with or without microalbuminuria and differences among the diabetic groups were statistically significant, which implies that this enzyme is a sensitive marker of tubular damage and could be used as a clinical utility for the detection of early stage of DN even in normoalbuminuric patients.

Earlier research has also shown that low baseline concentrations of urinary NAG were significantly associated with the regression of microalbuminuria over a subsequent 2 year treatment period, indicating that tubular dysfunction is a critical component of the early course of DN and that urinary NAG assessment may help in assessing this regression.¹⁵

Majority of the patients had a poor glycaemic control using the fasting blood glucose and HbA1c values. It has been postulated that diabetics with poor glycaemic control may be at higher risk of microalbuminuria. This was also expressed by Ekrikpo et al in a study at Uyo, Nigeriawhich showed that NAG excretion rate was higher in their diabetic subjects as majority of them had suboptimal blood glucose control.²⁴

When the urinary NAG/creatinine level was compared with HbA1c significant relationship was noted ($p=0.002$); same was observed that as HbA1C

values were elevated, there was a subsequent increase in the NAG/creatinine ratio. This may further affirm the relationship with persistently elevated glucose control as well as duration of diabetes with good control as previous research suggests that increased NAG and NAG/creatinine ratio values were observed to be associated with increase in duration of diabetes.⁴³

In Conclusion, urinary NAG excretion is significantly higher in microalbuminuric than in normoalbuminuric diabetic patients representing an early marker of incipient diabetic nephropathy buttressing that early NAG excretion at elevated levels is a significant marker of susceptibility to DN and its assessment may help identify diabetics with predisposition to DN.

Conflict of Interest

All authors in this study declare that there are no conflicts of interest. All authors had access to the study data, take responsibility for the accuracy of the analysis and had authority over the manuscript preparation and the decision to submit the manuscript for publication.

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